

Short Communication

PROJECTUAL CAPACITY OF THE HUMAN BRAIN: LINK BETWEEN NEWTONIAN PHYSICS AND QUANTUM PHYSICS

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Abstract

The AA, having taken note of the difficulties encountered by physicists in ascertaining that Quantum Physics does not respond to the traditional rules that govern Newtonian Physics, present, within the context of their experience gained in the study of the properties of the human brain, their hypothesis of a correlation between the two physics, identified in the projectual Capacity (PC) which is the result of brain activity, so “infinitely small”, quantum, that it cannot be perceptible by an external observer except through its realization in the context of Newtonian Physics.

KEY WORDS: Projectual capacity, (PC)- quantum physics – newtonian physics – neuronal network -thought

Introduction

The AA present this hypothesis of theirs as the primum movens of a new direction of research in Biophysics, capable of investigating the properties of the human brain which reverses the current process followed by Physics, of a knowledge of reality mediated by the five senses, to the taking of awareness of a quantum cerebral correlation capable, through the interference of a Projectual Capacity, of creating a precise reality even different from the Newtonian one.

The three dimensions that define Space in Newtonian Physics, and the fourth, Time, introduced by Albert Einstein as well as the theories of relativity are not reflected in Quantum Physics.

Space, defined in Newtonian physics by the three coordinates, exists only as a consequence of the movement of the object/subject within the three Cartesian axes alpha, beta and gamma, thus being able to define a flat, three-dimensional or curved space described by Einstein Time it does not exist, it is a fictitious concept, linked exclusively to the movement of the object in space.

A first element of contact between Newtonian physics and Quantum Physics is precisely this, that the concept of Time and Space requires an external interaction, observer or otherwise, to be brought into reality.

In Quantum Physics in particular, the phenomenon of entanglement between two particles having the same origin as demonstrated by Alain Aspect in 1982, who, validating Bohr's theory, he highlighted that until two

particles are observed their spins remain undefined, even in Newtonian Physics is the sole presence of the observer that interferes with the system and affects everyday reality.

At the brain level there is a quantum wave function linked to the brain activity of individual cells: this wave function remains undefined until an external interference intervenes which defines its quantum state or quantum correlation, therefore it is the neuronal activity that generates the indefinite function, but what we define as Projectual Capability (PC) is the external interference that produces the idea by defining the quantum state and translating it into Newtonian reality.

The Projectual Capacity is an exclusive property of the human brain. No other living animals or plant being, despite instinctively creating works of extraordinary complexity (a beehive, a spider web) is unable to realize any thing different (Instinctual Capacity).

Projectual capacity

This Projectual Capacity (PC) is the result of a well-documented brain activity as a consequence of a precise biological activity of a huge neuronal network (the estimated number of neurons in the human brain is 10^{11}). This neuronal activity, at the moment is expressed as a Projectual Capacity and can only be documented as an energetic expression, physically measurable as an electrical activity, but this, which we commonly define as “thought” so infinitely small (quantum) that it cannot be documented in its complex planning form translates, to following an external interaction, the idea, in a macroscopic material realization, and this is the **link between Quantum Physics and Newtonian Physics**.

To understand the importance of our observation we must consider that all daily reality (objects, vehicles, buildings, including products of literary activity, etc.) is the macroscopic Newtonian consequence of a "thought" (brain activity) so infinitely small as to cannot be documented either visually or with any instrumentation currently available.

If I think of lifting my arm, this thought, the result of my brain activity, so infinitely small (quantum) that it cannot be observed by an external subject, translates into a movement of the arm that responds to all the laws of Newtonian physics, gravity, movement, space, time etc.

CONCLUSIONS

This work, of which the Authors claim the priority of invention, opens an important window on the world of Physics as currently perceived, introducing new problems on the perception of reality today passively received by the five senses and reconstructed as such at a cerebral level, but which starting from a reverse process from the brain through its quantum design capacity, we become aware of the possibility of building a new reality beyond the reality currently perceived by the five senses.

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